

Symbolic Markov-chain-based music algorithm

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Abstract: In the article, there are explained differences between the symbolic type of music algorithm and the acoustic one. The algorithm's detailed structure and its relevance to the concept of probabilistic automaton are also described. Exemplary musical results of the used method are presented in the form of MIDI and audio files. Despite many created algorithms exists, the author decided to make the new one completely from the scratch. This solution means that the algorithmic melody generation method outlined in the article may incorporate some relatively novel elements; however, some constraints must also be considered.

Keywords: *algorithmic composition, music information retrieval, probabilistic automaton, computational musicology*

The Acoustic and the Symbolic Type of Algorithm – the Main Characteristics and Differences

Before the precise description of the used method, it has to be marked that the used algorithm is the symbolic type one. That means it operates on this kind of musical features which are explicitly notated in the music notation system (Cambouropoulos 1998; Cope 1989). It is the entirely different approach to the problem than the acoustic type of algorithm, which makes use of physical features of the signal, and which makes limitations caused by simplified musical notation irrelevant. On the other hand, a huge computational complexity emerges. The difference can be easily spotted even when taking into account only those features which are precisely notated in the musical notation, i.e. note pitch and note length information. Assuming – quite arbitrarily – the smallest frequency step Δf equal to 1 Hz, the approximate number of audible pitches is equal to 20,000. To compare, in the musical notation, there are approximately 128 possible pitches. The smallest time resolution Δt can be – again quite arbitrarily – assumed as equal to 1 msec. When considering duration of musical sounds, such small time resolution seems completely unnecessary. At the same time, broadening this resolution would cause a loss of many acoustically relevant information. When assuming the maximum duration of single musical sound equals to 4 seconds – the duration of whole note played at 60 beats per minute – we can count the number of all possible combinations of single sound pitch and duration, which equals to: $20,000 \times 4,000 = 80,000,000$. This range is the maximum one, and making use of it would be pointless. Actual musical pitch range consists of smaller number of frequencies and duration of musical sounds can be surely quantized in some way. The problem emerges when taking into account realities of performing music. Even musical pitch starts to be problematic in this view because exact pitch of musical sounds, which is stable in the frequency domain for longer time periods, can vary – from one recording to another and from one instrument to another. Sound duration is nearly impossible

to conceptualize. When music starts to be the subject of interpretation, default sound durations shorten and lengthen. The other thing is that both while performing and hearing music, onset time of sound is more important than its length. Here, the main advantage of symbolic notation appears, which is the elasticity caused by the level of abstraction. Sound duration in the symbolic notation is based on a division of specific rhythmic values, which can have a different sound duration, depending on a given tempo and momentary agogic changes. When taking the symbolic type of algorithm into account, the number of all possible combinations of single note pitch and duration is relatively small. We can assume the pitch range used in the MIDI standard and the shortest rhythmic value as the sixteenth note (thirty-second notes are used relatively rarely). The number of all possible first notes equals then to: $128 \times 5 = 640$. The number of all possible transitions from one note to the next is then equal to: $640 \times 640 = 409,600$. While generating monophonic melodies, this number grows exponentially with every following note. When generating a melody of N notes length, a number of all possible combinations equals to 640^N . Although this number grows significantly with every following note, it is still relatively small in comparison to the number of all possible combinations when using the acoustic type of algorithm.

The exemplary difference between the complexity of physical sound notation and musical notation can be seen on the Figure 1. The physical record, i.e. the spectrogram, operates on a very large amount of data, which in turn allows for their more detailed analysis, but this translates into much greater computational complexity. In the time domain, new information appears at intervals of few milliseconds. In the frequency domain, assuming the smallest possible frequency threshold approaching to zero, the amount of information is practically infinite. In comparison, musical notation uses much less information and, consequently, operations performed on it require much less computational complexity. In the domain of time, or rather rhythm, the smallest rhythmic value

can be taken as a sixteenth note or a thirty-two note. In the domain of frequency, or rather musical pitch, quantization takes place at every semitone.

Figure 1. The same melody notated as: a) up: spectrogram, b) down: musical notation. Adapted from: <http://musanim.com/mam/vttext.html>.

The additional advantage of the symbolic type of algorithm is the independence of analyzed features from timbre issues and individual interpretations. Music written in the symbolic way can be played on various instruments and sang by various voice types. It is also possible to perform it in various acoustic circumstances like room or open field properties. Further, the symbolic notation enables a subsequent musical interpretation by particular musicians. Even those features which are written down by a composer, related to agogic and dynamic changes, are not precise and their interpretation varies, depending on an individual performer or even on a specific record. Also, the symbolic notation represents a categorical perception of musical sounds (Wolfe 2002). Musicians hearing musical sounds which are out of tune or „out of time”, i.e. played or sang with an imprecise timing, can still properly write down a musical dictation based on those sounds. To sum up, the chosen music representation seems to feature what should be defined as the most

universal attributes of music. However, it has to be marked that music is not only a musical notation. To specify, this way of representing music is a product of cultural evolution. It is historically derivative to its layer which can be actually heard, similar to the fact that language characters are derivative to speech (Dukaj 2019).

The Syntactic Approach to Melodies Generation

Because of the use of symbolic data, the overall structure of the algorithm is similar to the model called probabilistic automaton (Bernabeu et al. 2011; Olugbenga and Adekunle 2014; Rabin 1963). It is a system which uses probability theory to generate sequences. Its main application is language generation, which is the base of all Large Language Models (LLM) like ChatGPT (Titus 2024). The interesting thing is that it can be just as easily applied to music. This reveals the overall similarity of language and music in terms of computational analysis and generation (Hirata et al. 2022). The roots of this similarity lies in semiotics of language and music, and particularly in the theory of syntax (Chomsky 1965), which with equal success applies both to language and music (Patel 2003). This basic method is sufficient to analyze and generate individual symbols or their sequences. However, there is another thing which is not included in this kind of computation, which is the higher level of analysis called semantics (Patel 2003). Here arise problems nearly impossible to be solved. At the level of language, there exist very effective methods to analyze this kind of semantics, but in the case of music, it is very hard to describe what musical semantics itself are. This is because of lack of direct designation of music to the real world objects. However, this problem is not in the scope of this algorithm and article. The author used syntactic method similar to probabilistic automaton to create a compositional algorithm and did not use any semantic layer to be included in the construction of the algorithm.

Infinite Monkey Theorem – the Musical Analogy and the Way to Overcome the Problem

A very interesting concept related to both language and music generation is the infinite monkey theorem (Borel 1913). It is a well-known thought experiment saying that when considering an infinite number of monkeys, which type on a typewriter keyboard for an infinite amount of time, we can assume they will write all existing texts, plus all possible texts in the future. The main problem of the theorem lies in assuming that monkeys hit keys in an absolutely random manner. It makes wanted outcomes impossible due to incredibly low probabilities of writing meaningful sentences. In the terms of law of truly large numbers (Diaconis and Mosteller 1989), the wanted outcomes would probably be achieved in an infinite amount of time. However, when thinking about real world applications, we have to modify the basic assumptions of this thought experiment, if we want to gain any satisfying outcomes. This thought experiment is a great analogy of syntactic approach described earlier, but at the same time, it has a one huge difference. The probability distribution of hitting several keys one after another is random. What we can observe is that monkeys in this thought experiment did not take any existing works as an input, which could cause them to learn actual syntactic rules. It is highly debatable if those monkeys could write anything with actual meaning only with syntactic rules and without any grammar ones or semantic clues. However, the latter ones emerge from the former (Patel 2003), so even this more primitive layer could give desirable outcomes in the end. The process would then be stochastic, but not random.

Moving to music realm, this theorem can be easily seen as an analogy, i.e. the task of monkeys would be writing all possible melodies. Instead of letters, there would be an alternative typewriter keyboard – a really huge one – with all possible pitches assigned to all possible rhythmic values. The other form of keyboard could be the less abstract one, i.e. real MIDI controller. Regardless

the physical medium, it is obvious that when considering the random approach, it would end in the same failure as in a language version. The solution would be exactly the same, i.e. giving monkeys the actual, existing musical works as an input to learn from it, and to make use of those syntactic rules in a melody generation. This is the way in which this particular, created algorithm works. It is valuable to mark this mechanism before describing its detailed, mathematical features, to understand the general principle standing behind its efficiency – learning. It is nothing new in terms of artificial intelligence basics, especially in machine learning techniques (Kostek 2021; Paiement 2008). However, because the described method is not an exact part of machine learning and artificial intelligence, it is worth mentioning that learning from the input is still a crucial part of the overall process.

Algorithmic Method

Below, there are described all specified steps of the algorithm, including music data representation, the used mathematical model and the detailed algorithm structure. There is also described the way of instrumentation of melodies as well as the additional option which is their computational analysis.

Music Data Representation

As written in the previous chapter, the implemented way of representing music is the symbolic notation. However, it does not mean that it should be understood literally as the musical notation itself. This notation represented as a data structure readable to a computer takes the format known as MIDI (Music Information Digital Interface) (Eerola and Toiviainen 2004). It is the type of simplified musical information, which can be easily loaded and exported. MIDI format itself is not the type of information on which operations needed to algorithmize music can take place.

This information has to be loaded into a specialized MIDI library and takes shape known as a *notematrix*, i.e. a matrix containing all sufficient musical information. The exemplary notematrix can be seen on Figure 2. Further operations take place on this representation, i.e. making use of vectors and matrices.

ONSET (BEATS)	DURATION (BEATS)	MIDI channel	MIDI PITCH	VELOCITY	ONSET (SEC)	DURATION (SEC)
nmat =						
0	0.9000	1.0000	64.0000	82.0000	0	0.5510
1.0000	0.9000	1.0000	71.0000	89.0000	0.6122	0.5510
2.0000	0.4500	1.0000	71.0000	82.0000	1.2245	0.2755
2.5000	0.4500	1.0000	69.0000	70.0000	1.5306	0.2755
3.0000	0.4528	1.0000	67.0000	72.0000	1.8367	0.2772
3.5000	0.4528	1.0000	66.0000	72.0000	2.1429	0.2772
4.0000	0.9000	1.0000	64.0000	70.0000	2.4490	0.5510
5.0000	0.9000	1.0000	66.0000	79.0000	3.0612	0.5510
6.0000	0.9000	1.0000	67.0000	85.0000	3.6735	0.5510
7.0000	1.7500	1.0000	66.0000	72.0000	4.2857	1.0714

Figure 2. The exemplary notematrix. Adapted from (Eerola and Toiviainen 2004).

The Analysis and the Synthesis of Music Data

The overall process of analysis and synthesis can be represented as follows. In the analysis part, at first, there is a human composer who creates new music in the form of sheet music. Then, this form of musical notation has to be transformed to the MIDI format. It can be done manually, by ear or by using existing MIDI files. Another way is not related to musical notation itself, but to actual recordings of piece performance. By using relevant software, we can automatically transform audio files to a MIDI data and a corresponding sheet music. When using this method, it is necessary to correct mistakes done by the program. After gaining the necessary MIDI file, it has to be loaded into the specialized library (Eerola and Toiviainen 2004). When using functions of this library, MIDI information is automatically transformed to the form of notematrix.

The synthesis part is almost an inversion of analysis one. At first, when having a notematrix, we have to export it as MIDI information. Then, we can use a virtual instrument to make it sound, and also record it as an audio file. It can be also left in a non-sounding form and be transcribed to the form of sheet music.

Mathematical Model

The mathematical model used in the process of generating melodies is known as the Markov chains (Cambouropoulos 1998; McAlpine et al. 1999; Highams and Olszewska 2023; Pachet et al. 2001; Seto 2022). It is the mathematical way of predicting subsequent elements of sequence, which lasts in time, and it is based on the probability theory. It is known from the broad use in many fields. It can be used to predict weather changes, financial market or to generate text and music (Pachet et al. 2001). It is the method which is old and well tested. The outcomes of the described algorithm confirm its efficiency. Its potential to use it in artificial intelligence creative systems has been even proved by passing the so-called “Musical Turing test” (Highams and Olszewska 2023), which is the ultimate measure of musical creative system quality. Figure 3 presents a simple diagram describing the overall process of Markov chains.

Figure 3. The simple Markov chain example for the A, C-sharp, and E-flat notes, showing the probabilities from one note to the next (Seto 2022).

Algorithm Structure

The process of generating algorithmic melodies is presented in this part of the article, in a step-by-step manner, to make it comprehensible. It is also possible to compare the following description with the code realizing the program, which is available [here](#). The specific lines refer to the “I” script, which structure is almost the same as other ones.

I) MIDI Sequence Load (lines 1-13)

An output melody is a statistical recombination of input melody. It is then necessary to load an input melody first. Input melody has to meet the two criteria:

- a) It has to consist of single sounds occurring at once. In other words, there should not occur multiple onsets. The algorithmization applies to monophonic melodies and not to polyphonic music containing full harmony.
- b) There should not be rests at all, i.e. time breaks between sounds. It can be easily prepared in DAW programs (Digital Audio Workstations) which are commonly used to MIDI data processing. Rhythmic values can be changed there in the way enabling both breaks and overlap removal.

The use of single monophonic melody as an input has to be justified by the aim of algorithmization. Melodies are to be maximally similar to each other in the case of being based on already existing ones in the most possible precise way. It has a high value in a relation to creating melodies, which are competitive to those created by humans. However, it has a very low analytical value, understood as musical knowledge extraction from musical works (Müllensiefen et al. 2008).

To achieve this aim – irrelevant from the perspective of this particular algorithm – whole datasets should be analyzed. One of the possible ways to do this is using this particular algorithm in an analysis of many melodies following each other, contained in a specified musical or compositional style.

II) Extraction of Pitch and Time Information (lines 14-22)

A *notematrix* is a whole matrix, which makes using it more difficult. It is then necessary to extract those features, which are relevant to a process of generating melodies. Parameters to be analyzed are pitch and time information. Loudness (velocity) was omitted because of the interpretative nature of this feature.

III) Markov Chain Order Choice (lines 23-25)

An order of a Markov chain determines a number of previous sequence elements, based on which a probability of occurrence of the following sequence element can be computed. In the case of melody sequence, those sequence elements are single musical notes which can be understood as sounds with a specific pitch and duration.

The choice of specific chain order determines the degree of randomness of algorithmic melody. The higher chain order, the smaller degree of randomness. In other words, the more of preceding notes are taken into the process of analysis and predicting a following element of sequence by the algorithm, the more determined is an output, algorithmized sequence. The lowest chain order which is possible to use is the 1st. In this case, output tends to have a large degree of randomness. The highest chain order which is reasonable in melody generation is the 9th. Then, in most cases, a replication takes place, i.e. an information is duplicated (Cohen 1962). The intuitive, graphical representation of those computations can be seen on Figure 4.

Figure 4. The graphical representation of the Markov order on the sheet music. The red rectangles indicate the 1st order (i.e. two notes analyzed at a time) and the blue rectangles indicate the 5th order (i.e. six notes analyzed at a time).

IV) Transition Matrix Computation (lines 26-80)

Figure 5 presents an exemplary transition matrix. It is a table containing all possible preceding sequence elements as well as following ones together with probabilities of those transitions. For this purpose, at first, a frequency of occurrence of sequence with N elements (notes) in a given melody is computed. N denotes a Markov chain order. Further, frequency of occurrence of a sequence with $N+1$ elements is computed. Transition probabilities are computed by a division of frequency of occurrence of sequence with N elements by a frequency of occurrence of sequence with $N+1$ elements. In other words, those are probabilities of occurrence of a specific note following a specific preceding sequence of notes.

12x12 Note Transition Matrix M=

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0.31 & 0.01 & 0.08 & 0.01 & 0.10 & 0.02 & 0.11 & 0.04 & 0.02 & 0.10 & 0.06 & 0.12 \\ 0.02 & 0.34 & 0.08 & 0.03 & 0.07 & 0.03 & 0.12 & 0.03 & 0.06 & 0.05 & 0.02 & 0.14 \\ 0.08 & 0.07 & 0.35 & 0.00 & 0.08 & 0.02 & 0.11 & 0.08 & 0.02 & 0.05 & 0.05 & 0.09 \\ 0.04 & 0.07 & 0.01 & 0.28 & 0.14 & 0.04 & 0.13 & 0.04 & 0.06 & 0.08 & 0.03 & 0.09 \\ 0.05 & 0.04 & 0.10 & 0.03 & 0.35 & 0.01 & 0.11 & 0.08 & 0.04 & 0.06 & 0.03 & 0.09 \\ 0.06 & 0.07 & 0.07 & 0.03 & 0.10 & 0.26 & 0.12 & 0.05 & 0.05 & 0.09 & 0.04 & 0.07 \\ 0.04 & 0.03 & 0.06 & 0.03 & 0.10 & 0.02 & 0.34 & 0.07 & 0.03 & 0.08 & 0.07 & 0.12 \\ 0.04 & 0.02 & 0.05 & 0.01 & 0.09 & 0.01 & 0.16 & 0.36 & 0.02 & 0.08 & 0.05 & 0.11 \\ 0.04 & 0.12 & 0.04 & 0.03 & 0.10 & 0.04 & 0.10 & 0.04 & 0.25 & 0.09 & 0.05 & 0.10 \\ 0.07 & 0.03 & 0.06 & 0.01 & 0.05 & 0.02 & 0.11 & 0.10 & 0.04 & 0.34 & 0.04 & 0.12 \\ 0.06 & 0.02 & 0.10 & 0.01 & 0.07 & 0.02 & 0.18 & 0.09 & 0.03 & 0.09 & 0.22 & 0.12 \\ 0.04 & 0.06 & 0.07 & 0.01 & 0.09 & 0.01 & 0.11 & 0.06 & 0.03 & 0.11 & 0.05 & 0.35 \end{bmatrix}$$

Where the elements are [C C# D D# E F F# G G# A A# B]

Figure 5. The note transition matrix containing 12 rows and 12 columns for all 12 notes of the chromatic scale. Adapted from (Seto 2022).

V) Algorithmic Melody Generation (lines 81-141)

This is the part of the algorithm which refers not only to a data analysis but also to its generation. Despite the fact that it is not the necessary part of the process, defining a first note explicitly by a user was implemented in the algorithm. This operation reduces a number of possible melodies, but at the same time it makes outputs – out of necessity – more similar to an input melody. A length (a number of sequence elements) of algorithmized melody can be unlimited. However, from the perspective of similarity, it was desirable to set this length at a level of input melody. As a result, an output melody has the same number of notes as an input melody. A physical duration of melodies is not the same, but a number of notes is a better musical parameter. A choice and addition of a specific note to an already existing sequence takes place by drawing possible following elements with a defined probability. A generation works in a step-by-step

manner (iteratively) – the algorithm moves an analysis window by one note ahead. Particular probabilities have to sum up to 1, but their distribution can take various forms. In the effect, a choice of specific note is characterized by a high degree of randomness. Consequently, an output melody can seem more or less random but statistical features remain the same. Those are important features, which allows recognizing an overall musical style.

Computational Analysis of Melody (lines 142-161)

An actual listening to those algorithmic melodies depends on several factors such as musical knowledge, musical style familiarity, attitude, expectations or bias against computer generated music (Moffat and Kelly 2006; Pasquier et al. 2016; Piccione 2023; Samson and Coronel 2021; Zlatkov et al. 2023). The interesting method of objective evaluation of generated melody is its computational comparison with an input melody (Jiang et al. 2022; Müllensiefen and Frieler 2004). Computational parameters are included in the MIDI Toolbox library, which purpose was to make a complex computational analysis of melody possible (Eerola and Toivainen 2004). Exemplary parameters are melody similarity, complexity, tonality, originality and melodiousness.

Instrumentation

A raw output of the algorithm is a pure numerical matrix converted to a MIDI format. It is sufficient in terms of computational analysis, but not from the perspective of using it as music which can be actually heard by a listener. To make it sound, a new MIDI information has to be loaded into a DAW program and instrumented by a timbre according to user's needs.

Results

The desired format for presenting the results of the described algorithm is primarily musical notation. However, this type of transcription from MIDI files is ineffective due to the huge number of errors made by the programs. Therefore, it was decided to present the results in the form of only MIDI files and, above all, sound files (in .wav format). Sample effects can be found at [this page](#). Due to the good availability of MIDI recordings of classical music found on [specialized pages](#), the results are mainly for this genre of music, but additional effects for a popular jazz theme are also included for comparison. When listening and analyzing the results and comparing them with the original counterparts, several conclusions can be made.

1) The use of the 1st order Markov chain allows to obtain the most diverse, creative and original effects, while maintaining the overall musical style and underlying harmony. At the same time, the melodic contour is not preserved at all, which creates large, random interval jumps, making it impossible to recognize individual motifs, phrases and musical sentences. The use of the 1st order is a good solution for pieces from the etude repertoire and jazz improvisations, but it does not work well for structured themes, e.g. fugues, cantilena melodies and vocal repertoire.

2) The use of the 2nd order Markov chain allows for more consistent effects. Although they lose diversity, creativity and originality, they clearly better reproduce the musical structures contained in the original. However, due to random moments of "breaking" the phrase, it is impossible to obtain a complete musical sentence, and the beat is not fully preserved. Even so, it is still a better reproduction of the original melodic, harmonic and rhythmic structures than when using the 1st order.

3) The use of higher orders of the Markov chain makes the effects more and more resemble ordinary replication, i.e. reproduction of the original musical information on a 1:1 scale. Even with longer fragments, the 5th order is sufficient for replication to occur. Using higher orders is therefore completely pointless, but orders from 1 to 10 have been appended to the code to make it more complementary.

4) In general, to generate musically good effects, it is necessary to repeat the generation process at least several times. For this reason, a very valuable next step to improve the functionality of the algorithm would be the implementation of a GUI (Graphical User Interface), enabling both loading the input melody, selecting the order of the Markov chain and the "generate" function.

5) Along with the melodies, computational parameters are also generated, such as: the distance between the input and output melody, the complexity of both melodies, their tonality, originality and melodiousness. Using larger data sets, these calculations can be compared for different types of melodies, which would allow for their objective, computational assessment.

Conclusion

Overall, the point of the article was to present the method of generation of algorithmic melodies, which base on those composed by humans. The mathematical model used in this method bases on the Markov chains (Cambouropoulos 1998; McAlpine et al. 1999; Pachet et al. 2001; Seto 2022). The results are statistical recombination of input melodies, which can be called „musical mimicsies”. The very important issue is that the presented algorithm cannot be defined as artificial intelligence. The main reason is that the level of automation is too low, and the user has to control too many aspects of the process, especially when it comes to MIDI issues. This way of implementation was chosen consciously because the main approach focused on gaining

the insight into the process and making it possible to control all the parameters. Nevertheless, it is of course possible to improve and automate the algorithm to the extent, which will allow classifying it as an artificial intelligence (Highams and Olszewska 2023).

The main advantage of using the Markov chains is maintaining a musical style of melodies (Cambouropoulos 1998; Youngblood 1958). Generated melodies seem to be more or less random, but they always remain within a specific musical style. The crucial conclusion is that compositional rules which are consciously used by human composers are not necessary to reflect this musical feature. The pure statistical approach turned out to be sufficient. Similar conclusions were made while comparing music to language (Hirata et al. 2022). Both systems of communication make use of following sequence elements. Those elements can be organized by rules, statistics or a combination of those. The powerful feature of statistical approach is the flexibility, which can easily cope with the problematic attribute of both music and language systems, which is their historical and cultural variability (Müllensiefen et al. 2008). Then, this method can be described as culturally invariant. Its efficiency is the same for all types of music, including Dodecaphony, where the statistical distribution of pitch classes is entirely flat. It can be also applied to music from other cultures, but only if the smallest interval between particular pitches is the half tone. It could be an interesting investigation, allowing research out of the circle of Western Tonal Music, which is mainly based on the major and minor modes. The main difficulty is transcribing music from another culture to the MIDI format, but it can be done also by ear.

On the other hand, from the semiotic perspective, the statistical approach to music and language allows analyzing the syntactic structure of a given communication system but not its semantics (Patel 2003). It has to be marked that despite an overall efficiency in using the syntactical analysis

to algorithmize music and language data, this approach does not allow extracting the most important phenomenon – meaning. Which, in music, is very hard to discover.

Limitations

The limitations of the used method are as follows:

- a) The use of the symbolic algorithm implies that it is impossible to obtain results, which would be enabled by the acoustic algorithm. The use of the second type is the only way to analyze and algorithmize music, which bases mainly or only on timbre changes and not on changes of sound pitch and duration. The type of music that is here in the scope of interest is mainly the Electronic Music, especially the Electroacoustic Music, in which the degree of acoustical processing of natural sounds is very high. A musical score of this type of music can be only transcribed as a physical representation, i.e. a spectrogram.
- b) The author found it very hard to implement the realization of full musical harmony, or any harmony at all. To include this very important feature of music, it would be necessary to solve the problem relating to the analysis of many notes occurring at once.
- c) The existence of meter in output melodies is debatable. Thanks to maintaining statistical features of melodies written by humans, beat tends to be preserved. However, the degree of this preservation is not sufficient to make the precise definition of meter possible. The final consequence is that meter tends to break down.
- d) As said before, the algorithm cannot be classified as artificial intelligence because of too low level of automation.

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